

Determination of Second Dissociation Constant of 7-nitro-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic Acid by EMF Method

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7-nitro-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic acid is dibasic. From the preliminary investigation, it was found that the ratio of k_{D1}/k_{D2} was greater than 10^3 . Hence the treatment of monobasic acid to determine pk_D may be applied to the second stage of dissociation constant. The titration technique was used to determine Bronsted constant (pk'_{D2}), using Henderson equation. pk'_{D2} was determined at various ionic strengths. The graph of pk'_{D2} against VI was plotted. The limiting slope of the curve was found to be -1.58 , agreeing well with the theoretical value of -1.57 at 40° . The thermodynamic value of pk_{D2} obtained on extrapolation to zero ionic strength is 5.72 ± 0.02 .

The 7-nitro-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic acid (henceforth, abbreviated as NQSA) was first prepared by Molland¹ and its dissociation constants were determined by Nasanen and Uusitalo²; and Fresco and Freiser³. Nasanen and Uusitalo determined the dissociation constants by measuring pH of 1/4th and 3/4th neutralized solution of NQSA by standard alkali and varying ionic strength by addition of KCl. The thermodynamic values were evaluated by applying extended form of Debye-Hückel-Bronsted equation for activity coefficient and calculating by least square method. They have reported thermodynamic values of pk_{D1} and pk_{D2} as 1.95 and 5.75 at 25° respectively. Fresco and Freiser determined stoichiometric dissociation constants and they reported pk_{D1} (spectrophotometrically at 28°) and pk_{D2} (potentiometrically at 25°) as 0.4 and 5.62 respectively. Nasanen and Uusitalo calculated pk_D values by rigorous calculation but their method of determination of pk_D was not reliable as evident from the reported value of pk_{D1} ; the value is much higher than that reported by Fresco and Freiser. We have also found out first dissociation constant by conductance method⁴ ($pk_{D1} = 0.55$) which is in agreement with that of Fresco and Freiser rather than that of Nasanen and Uusitalo. Fresco and Freiser also followed approximate half \bar{n}_H method to evaluate pk_{D2} . Thus, both the workers have not followed the rigorous method for the determination of pk_{D2} . Hence in present investigation, the second dissociation constant of NQSA was reinvestigated by e.m.f. method.

From the equation for second dissociation constant of any acid H_2L , $k_{D2} = a_H \times a_{L^{2-}} / a_{HL^-}$, the following equation⁵ is derived from the determination of pk_{D2} from the pH measurement of partly neutralized solution of acid

$$pH = pk_{D2} + \log \frac{B}{a - B} + \log \frac{f_{L^{2-}}}{f_{HL^-}} \quad (1)$$

On rearrangement equation (1), we have,

$$pH = (pk_{D_2} + \log f_{L^{--}} - \log f_{HL^-}) + \log \frac{B}{a-B} \quad (2)$$

or

$$pH = pk'_{D_2} + \log \frac{B}{a-B} \quad (3)$$

where

$$k'_{D_2} = a_{H^+} \cdot \frac{m_{L^{--}}}{m_{HL^-}} \quad (4)$$

k'_{D_2} is Bronsted or mixed constant and includes correction for activity coefficient of hydrogen ion but not for HL^- and L^{--} ions. In above equations, a , m and f represent activity, molality and activity coefficient of respective species; a = initial amount of acid and $B = b + m_{H^+} - m_{OH^-}$, where b is the amount of base added. k'_{D_2} is related to thermodynamic value of K_{D_2} by equation

$$K_{D_2} = k'_{D_2} \cdot \frac{f_{L^{--}}}{f_{HL^-}} \quad (5)$$

If the values of pk'_{D_2} at different ionic concentrations are available, the thermodynamic value of pk_{D_2} can be obtained by graphical extrapolation of the curve of pk'_{D_2} against \sqrt{I} where ' I ' is ionic strength. The limiting slope of the curve should be equal to $-3A = -1.572$ at 40° (for a dibasic acid).

Fig 1

EXPERIMENTAL

The stock 0.05M solution of NQSA was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of NQSA in hot water, cooling to room temperature and then diluting to the desired volume.

This solution was standardized against standard alkali using phenolphthalein as an indicator. (The method of standardizing NQSA solution, even though being of yellow colour, against standard alkali using phenolphthalein as an indicator was established in our laboratory by comparing results with that of potentiometric method and was found quite satisfactory, accurate and speedy). Standard solution of carbonate free NaOH was prepared and standardized by usual method. All chemicals used were of A. R. or G.R. grade.

The equation (3) was used to determine pk'_{D_2} . For this, titration technique was followed. 50 ml. of 1 mM, 5 mM and 10 mM NQSA solutions at various ionic strengths (maintained by using following concentration of KCl as background electrolyte : for 1 mM NQSA, 0.00, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.08, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8 M KCl were used; for 5 mM and 10 mM NQSA 0.00, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6 and 0.8 M KCl were used), were prepared and titrated against standard alkali potentiometrically at 40°, using Beckman expanded scale pH-meter (having accuracy of 0.01 pH unit and reproducibility of 0.005 pH unit). 1mM NQSA solutions were titrated against 0.020N NaOH; while 5 mM and 10 mM NQSA solutions were titrated against 0.203 N NaOH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The typical titration curves (pH against ml. of NaOH added) for 1 mM, 5 mM and 10 mM NQSA in 0.1 M KCl solution are depicted graphically in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

For sake of brevity other results are not given. From the figures, it is clear that 1 mole of NQSA consumes two moles of NaOH and two distinct jumps are obtained in the titration curve. The data of first neutralization portion could not be used for evaluation of first dissociation constant as it was found that species H_2L do not exist at pH 2.0 or above i.e., at pH 2.0 the first stage of dissociation of H_2L into H^+ and HL^- is virtually complete. In all titrations, initial pH was above 2.0. From the preliminary investigation, it was found that the ratio k_{D1}/k_{D2} was greater than 10^3 . Hence, data of second neutralization curve can be used for determination of second dissociation constant as a monobasic acid.

From the curve of pH against ml. of NaOH added, different points (between pH 4 and 6) were selected and the term $\log B/a-B$ was calculated. Then, pH was plotted against $\log B/a-B$ for each titration. The results for 1mM, 5 mM and 10 mM NQSA in 0.1 M KCl solutions are also depicted in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The values of pk'_{D2} obtained as an intercept are summarized in Table 1 with the value of slopes obtained which are in the range of 1 ± 0.01 . The value of pk'_{D2} is reported with an accuracy of ± 0.01 log unit.

The ionic strength required for plotting the curve of pk'_{D2} against \sqrt{I} , was calculated for each case at half neutralization as at this point $\log B/a-B$ is equal to zero and $pH = pk'_{D2}$. In calculation of ionic strength due account was given for the salt Na_2L , a 1 : 2 electrolyte formed by neutralization and also of volume change. The square root of ionic strength \sqrt{I} , for each case is also reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1

	Conc. of KCl (<i>M</i>)	pk'_{D_2}	\sqrt{I}^{+*}	Slope
1 <i>mM</i>	0.00	5.66	0.043	1.00
	0.005	5.58	0.081	1.00
	0.01	5.56	0.098	1.00
	0.02	5.50	0.143	1.00
	0.05	5.44	0.220	1.01
	0.08	5.40	0.276	0.99
	0.10	5.36	0.308	1.01
	0.20	5.27	0.434	1.00
	0.40	5.20	0.611	1.01
	0.60	5.16	0.748	1.01
5 <i>mM</i>	0.80	5.12	0.864	1.00
	0.00	5.56	0.098	1.00
	0.05	5.38	0.238	1.01
	0.10	5.35	0.326	1.01
	0.20	5.25	0.450	1.00
	0.40	5.20	0.623	1.00
	0.50	5.15	0.701	1.01
	0.60	5.14	0.767	1.01
10 <i>mM</i>	0.80	5.10	0.884	1.01
	0.00	5.50	0.137	1.00
	0.05	5.36	0.255	1.00
	0.10	5.34	0.335	1.00
	0.20	5.25	0.453	1.00
	0.40	5.20	0.626	1.00
	0.50	5.18	0.696	1.00
	0.60	5.18	0.760	1.00
	0.80	5.14	0.874	1.01

**I* represents the ionic strength at half neutralization.

TABLE 2

Workers	pk_{D_2}	Temp. °C	Remarks
Nasanen Uusitalo	5.75	25	Thermodynamic constant
Fresco and Freiser	5.62	25	Concentration constant in dilute solution
Present investigation	5.72	40	Thermodynamic constant

The graph of pk'_{D_2} against \sqrt{I} is shown in Fig. 4. The limiting slope of the curve is -1.58 and the thermodynamic value of pk_{D_2} obtained on extrapolation to zero ionic strength is 5.72 . The experimental value of slope agrees well with the theoretical value of $-3A = -1.572$ at 40° . This justifies the value of pk_{D_2} as 5.72 ± 0.02 at 40° .

The values of pk_{D_2} obtained in the present investigation along with that of previous workers are summarized in Table 2.

Uusitalo⁶ has reported pk_{D_2} of NQSA at 0° and 50° as 5.919 and 5.605. Hence, according to Nasanen and Uusitalo the value of pk_{D_2} will be about 5.66 at 40° . Fresco and Friersers' value of pk_{D_2} , when converted to 40° will be also of the same order. Taking into consideration the following two reasons, one may consider that present value of $pk_{D_2} = 5.72 \pm 0.02$ at 40° is reasonably acceptable; (1) In the present investigation stock solution of NQSA has been prepared of higher concentration as compared to both previous investigations. Both workers have reported that solubility of NQSA is too small and even to prepare dilute solution required vigorous stirring. Furthermore, in the present investigation, the stock solutions were standardized while previous workers prepared solution of NQSA by weight. NQSA has one mole of water of crystallization and it is efflorescent. (2) The experimental limiting slope of the curve pk'_{D_2} against \sqrt{I} in the present investigation agrees well with theoretical value justifying its reliability. Nasanen and Uusitalo have calculated the thermodynamic value of pk_{D_2} from stoichiometric ones without such experimental proof of the agreement of slope.

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